

An Investigation into the Subjective Experience of White Space in an Urban Environment

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Abstract

Two-dimensional graphic design teaches us that white space, often known as negative space, is an important design parameter which when uncontrolled, can result in visual emptiness. This article describes an investigation into how this phenomenon works on a grand architectural scale: the urban landscape. The researchers conducted short personal interviews in two urban plazas in Bergen, Norway. One urban plaza, Festplassen, represents an open area that employs a great degree of three-dimensional white space. For comparative purposes, we interviewed pedestrians in a non-white space plaza, Torgallmenningen. From these subjective opinions, the authors extracted six categories which cover all the responses which were generated. The results show that white space in an urban area creates an aesthetically pleasing plaza, but is not considered a sociable place to be. Respondents emphasized the importance of an urban space's social aspects by saying that they appreciated the Festplassen most when it was filled with people, entertainment venues, etc. This article concludes with the observation that in order to avoid being associated with emptiness, white space must be applied very conscientiously and sensitively. Even though it is the space between other objects, white space is a powerful determinant of how a composition communicates to its viewers, both in 2- and 3-dimensions.

1. Introduction

Visual composition employs a number of different design parameters to communicate a message. This message gives the viewer a cumulative impression and often results in the attachment of emotional characteristics to the composition. How well those parameters are combined and controlled determines the overall communicability of the composition. This study focuses on one important parameter of visual design known as *white space*.

Alex White alludes to the difficulty of designing with white space (White 2002) when he acknowledges that it is ignored by all but a few who consciously manipulate it to create contrast, drama and rest. Composers, sculptors, artists and architects use it. Armin Hofmann elaborates on this crucial design aspect by saying that it is the space in between, often a by-product, is just as important as the element that produces it (Hofmann 1965). As a design parameter, white space can be defined as "...the empty but often active areas that are void of visual elements" (Resnick, 2003). Nielsen refers to it as "unused" (Nielsen 2001). Despite this seemingly negative approach to white space, cultural experience tells us that consumers associate white space with high quality and/or exclusivity. This is an emotional association which can be very powerful. It is important to learn more about the value of visual purity and whiteness and its emotional associations. It is our observation that prominent use of white space seems to promote consistent emotions and associations across various media (product packaging, small boutiques, user-interface design). For this reason we chose to investigate the emotional associations on a grand three-dimensional (3D) scale: architectural space. This study investigates people's subjective experience of white space in three dimensions on a grand public scale. The focus of the study was to research user opinions of two open plazas that represent two very different architectural layouts.

The availability of public space determines the pulse of the city or town. Public space is an especially important arena because it is where people meet, and where the city's current culture and history connect. Hopefully the public space encourages people's participation in recreational habits, feelings of comfort, familiarity, etc. The Norwegian city of Bergen is one example where many city development projects have been implemented. One urban space in particular (Festplassen) employs a conscientious amount of three-dimensional, architectural white space. We chose to collect data about people's experiences in Torgallmenningen for comparison purposes. The data collection for Festplassen would become richer when compared with a different architectural area.

1.1 Primary Research Questions

Our hypothesis combines the two very different backgrounds and interests of the authors: graphic design and sociology. When applied successfully in 2D graphic design, white space can denote characteristics of quality and exclusivity, but when applied unsuccessfully, it can exemplify visual exclusivity. This phenomenon can be ascribed to the sociological experience of urban architectural space. When white space is applied successfully in landscape design, it can be considered beautiful, but antisocial. When applied unsuccessfully, it can be deemed a uninteresting public space. This study hypothesizes that people experience exclusivity on a grand architectural scale based on the amount of visual white space.

In this study, residents of Bergen were interviewed to determine their experience of white space in two outdoor urban spaces. Through the project, the intention was to gain insight about the overall perception and emotional associations generated by the different architectural design of the two plazas. It was determined that grounded theory approach was the most appropriate research tool, and data was to be collected based upon interviews conducted on the two sites.

2. The research sites

For this study, white space is relative. In order to see where white space *is used* in the urban arena, a second site was needed to characterize where white space *is not* used. For this reason, this study was devised to compare the relative engagement of white space between Torgallmenningen and Festplassen. The two urban spaces are conveniently located only 40 meters apart from each other. They provide an equivalent potential for pedestrian activity, and both plazas are equivalent in size.

2.1 Torgallmenningen

Identifying characteristics of Torgallmenningen include:

- Primary central location. Considered the reference point for *central*
- Often described as Bergen's living room.
- Enclosed by tall buildings and shops on three sides
- Long and narrow in shape
- Contains public benches which line each long side
- Contains a kiosk, trees, and several large statues
- The pavement is dark grey slate, especially when wet

Fig. 1: Torgallmenningen

Torgallmenningen is an old outdoor plaza located in the center of the city of Bergen and dates from 1582. It is both a non-motorized street and a public space. It was originally built as a buffer to prevent spread of fire: wide buffer streets maintain distance between buildings, especially old wooden buildings. Torgallmenningen is the largest of the numerous open plazas in Bergen, and its location in the middle of the city makes it one of the most visited public spaces in Bergen (Wathne and Bjørlykke 1998).

Torgallmenningen is located between the City Square to the east, to Olav V's Place to the west; it is closed for motorized traffic in the west. During the devastating city fire in 1916, Torgallmenningen was completely destroyed. Finn Berner, an architect from NTH in Trondheim, was given the responsibility to draw a new, improved Torgallmenning. Torgallmenningen has remained spatially unchanged since 1916, with relatively minor adjustments to accommodate the changing aesthetic tastes. New materials were added to the street floor at a later date, and in 2002, Bård Breivik's new columns in front of the shopping center. Both structural changes lead to a heated political debate in Bergen.¹

Torgallmenningen is surrounded by stone buildings with 5-6 floors. In most of the buildings there is a diverse mix of shops and offices, with shops on the 1st and 2nd floor. These buildings were built after the big city fire in 1916. The predominant architectural style at Torgallmenningen is New Classicism, and the only exception is the Functionalistic building Sundt Shopping Center, designed by Per Grieg in 1938 (Wathne and Bjørlykke 1998).

¹ Information from <http://no.wikipedia.org/wiki/Torgallmenningen>, 01.04.06.

The floor on Torgallmenningen consists of plates of dark grey slate. There are two very large sculptures: Sjøfartsmonumentet (Seaman's Monument) and Blå Stein (Blue Stone). In addition, there are numerous fountains, oversized flower planters, and various street amenities such as benches, mail- and phone boxes. Sitting in Torgallmenningen is popular: 28 benches plus more than 100 sitting places provide plenty of space for lounging, when the weather permits. Several restaurants and other service offices line the three sides of the plaza (Wathne and Bjørlykke 1998).

Due to its wide range of services and provisions, Torgallmenningen does not represent what this project defines as white space in a public room. The architecture style and commercial activity make Torgallmenningen a busy and crowded place with little white space to separate buildings, street equipment and people.

2.2 Festplassen

Identifying characteristics of Festplassen include:

- Located centrally, 40 meters from Torgallmenningen
- Often described as Bergen's *living room*
- Butted up against a sizable man-made pond, Lille Lungegårdsvann
- Trees on outer edges
- No benches
- The pavement is light grey granite

Fig. 2: Festplassen

Festplassen is the name of the 7000 sq m open space between Lille Lungegårdsvann, Rasmus Meyers allé, Christiesgate and Kaigaten. Until 2002, Festplassen was used as an urban parking area, while only occasionally serving as a location for entertainment activities such as Tivoli, circus groups, exhibitions or big outdoor concerts. Festplassen is often used for the location for the celebration of the national holiday, 17th of May, since 1929. (Bergen Byleksikon 2006²).

In 2002, Bergen County decided to convert Festplassen into a permanently traffic-free arena for cultural activities. The Architect Office, CUBUS Arkitekter AS, had been working with different plans for the area since the 1980s, and together with Bergen County and Kalve-Smedsvig Landskapsarkitekter AS, became responsible for the redesign process.

The reopening of Festplassen took place in 2004. It was now designed to be a flexible place for large public assemblies, as well as for everyday use. It is shaped in the form of a large quadratic square, with solid granite plates on the floor and in the walls that separate the square from the City Park. The square meets the city park on one side, Ole Bulls Plass on the opposite side, and has an open view against the small lake Lille Lungegårdsvann. Above Lille Lungegårdsvann the view continues unimpeded towards the mountains that surround Bergen city. At night, Festplassen is lighted dimly, thanks to the work by Arne Selen, LandskapDESIGN. Festplassen also provides a moderate amount of sitting area, there are eight benches designed by Elin Strandenes.

A kiosk and skateboard area have been planned, but are not yet complete. In 2002, the team consisting of Bergen County, CUBUS Architects AS, and Kalve-Smedsvig Landscape Architects AS were awarded the National Architectural Prize, Statens Byggekikkpris, for their combined work on Festplassen.

When not busy with an entertainment venue, Festplassen maintains a clean, sparse aesthetic style. It is characterized by the high quality of materials used in its decoration, and is a good representation of what this project defines as a white space in a public place. In three dimensions, Festplassen characterizes qualities of two-dimensional white space by being open,

² Partly available at <http://www.home.no/bergensiden/Leksikon.htm#F>.

spacious and free of visual clutter. More importantly, it was conscientiously designed to communicate those primary values to its viewers.

Fig. 3: The map used, very rarely, during the interviews

3. Method

The research study was carried out by the two authors in Bergen, Norway on Wednesday, 22 March 2006. Both researchers collected data from both urban spaces between 14:30 - 17:30 on a clear but cold winter day. To avoid potential interviewer bias, the researchers spent 1.5 hours interviewing pedestrians in both urban spaces *separately*, whereupon they switched places and spent another 1.5 hours in the opposite space. The researchers approached pedestrians randomly and asked an almost identical set of questions (see table below).

3.1 Interview Technique

64 subjects were interviewed — this number does not reflect the general population as a whole. Though not generalizable, this number provides an impression of how people *might* respond to the questions, and to how people *might* associate certain emotions with the respective urban spaces. The findings do not represent the opinion of all residents of Bergen, however, it is possible to extract predilections from the group of responses.

3.2 The Interview Questions

In the first two questions, the subjects were prompted to describe each plaza with three adjectives respectively. The prediction was that a majority of people would respond with neutral answers such as *nice*, or *large*. By then asking them to spend a few extra moments on the third question, we hoped to elicit more meaningful adjectives which might reflect their opinion more precisely. This was an effective technique which generated a large number of words outside of the neutral genre.

We asked the following questions as each plaza:

1. If you were to describe Torgallmenningen/Festplassen, with three adjectives, what would you say?
2. What do you like best about Torgallmenningen/Festplassen?
3. What would you like to change about Torgallmenningen/Festplassen?
4. Which public space do you prefer? (asked by one researcher only)
5. Subject details: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Gender• Residence• Profession

It is important to note that both researchers inquired about *both* plazas, while located in each one respectively. This was done in order to test the influence of physical location upon the respondents' answers. We wanted to determine if there was a difference in responses from when people were physically standing in one plaza vs. the other. This resulted in being a highly determinant factor in the responses.

3.3 Circumstantial Conditions

It was a cold day, and the weather varied between partly sunny and light snow. It was chilly and moderately populated. We had predicted to find more people in Torgallmenningen than Festplassen, which turned out to be true.

The interview process proceeded as planned for both interviewers. Both researchers noted that people were easier to approach at Torgallmenningen, most likely because they were more likely to wander around without a specific destination in mind. However, it was more difficult to approach people at Festplassen. We noted that people seemed to use the space as a passageway, and were more likely to proceed intentionally from one point to another. We

both felt that pedestrians at Festplassen were less willing to be disturbed en route to their destination. In addition, the presence of a patch of snow in the middle inhibited pedestrian traffic there, but this melted during the interview session.

3.4 Evaluation

The interviews resulted in a substantial amount of responses which we knew had to be organized in some way. We tallied all adjectives/responses and wrote each one onto an individual sticky note. Doing this allowed us to easily place the responses in relation to each other. After we grouped the answers, identifying characteristics rose out of each group which allowed us to assign a category name. In this manner, the responses determined the category names, and not our presupposition of what the categories should have been. This process resulted in six different categories which embodied the diversity of answers. The categories of answers are:

- **Situational/Material Descriptors**
Refers to words which describe the current situation and material qualities
(e.g. *under construction, benches, open, etc.*)
- **Symbolic Descriptors**
Refers to respondents' strong symbolic perceptions of the area
(e.g. *a symbol of Bergen, essence of Bergen, etc.*)
- **Physical Attribute Descriptors**
Refers to multiple visible parameters which affect the overall impression of the area
(e. g. *dirty, clean, filled with litter, etc.*)
- **Social Descriptors**
Refers to human activity in the area
(e.g. *meeting place, living room, creates life, etc.*)
- **Emotional Descriptors**
Refers to various feelings associated with the area
(e.g. *I like it, it's dead, I enjoy the weather here, etc.*)
- **Service/Activity Descriptors**
Refers to practical activities, provisions and events available in the area
(e.g. *shopping, concerts, 17th of May, etc.*)

These category titles will be referred to in the Results section.

3.5 Respondent Details

Both genders were represented equally: 50 % women, 50 % men. The majority of respondents lived in Bergen and the immediate area. Respondents represented a diverse range of professions. Because the interviews were conducted during the afternoon of a normal workday, there was a large base of students, retirees and shift workers. This factor might have been reduced had the interviews been conducted during the weekend.

4. Results & Discussion

This section will address the results for each plaza respectively.

4.1 Descriptors for Torgallmenningen vs. Festplassen

In general, respondents appeared to have a strong connection to Torgallmenningen. A majority of respondents described the area with emotional and socially-oriented characteristics. With regard to Festplassen, people appeared to appreciate and enjoy Festplassen's aesthetic design. They responded that it was beautiful, stylish, and lovely. However, they did not respond with the same emotional connection descriptors that they did with Torgallmenningen.

Fig. 4: Comparison of what respondents like best about Torgallmenningen and Festplassen

The following points reveal our insights into the responses of the emotional and the social descriptors.

Emotional Descriptors for Festplassen	Emotional Descriptors for Torgallmenningen
<p>Contrary to Torgallmenningen, people described Festplassen with Situational/Materialistic and Physical Attribute descriptors (e.g. naked, too modern, gray, simple). Even still, many respondents said that they liked the minimalist and simple design, at least aesthetically.</p> <p>Surprisingly many described the space as new.</p>	<p>They said that it is welcoming and grand. Many said that it is nice, and one woman said she loves it, as if it were a person.</p> <p>Four respondents said that it embodies the essence of Bergen. For these people, Torgallmenningen carries a strong symbolic character.</p> <p>Many said they enjoy the sun/level of activity/weather/lifestyle there.</p> <p>Of all respondents, there were only two who described Torgallmenningen with negative descriptors: boring and most monitored place in Norway.</p> <p>Nine people could not come up with anything they would want to change.</p>

The majority of people at Festplassen referred to Situational/Material categories to describe the urban plaza. Festplassen was described by the activities which are held there periodically. Some hoped that it was in the process of becoming a symbol of Bergen, but that it had not yet done so. Only one person mentioned sociable attributes and characteristics for Festplassen. People seemed to interpret the space as if it were a piece of art or sculpture, everyone referred to it as beautiful. Only a few thought of Festplassen as a grey, dull and empty public space.

Social Descriptors for Festplassen	Social Descriptors for Torgallmenningen
<p>Many respondents described the area as important for entertainment and activities.</p> <p>The area was described as practical, nice to have, an ok living room, good to use — aspects which mean that it is nice under certain conditions.</p> <p>Only one person mentioned that it was a social area.</p> <p>No one seemed to mind the lack of commercial activity, but many noted the lack of a satisfactory amount of activity and cultural possibilities</p>	<p>The majority of respondents consider the plaza to be an important social arena.</p> <p>Social-aspect descriptors often arose as one or more of the adjective list, whereas very few of those standing in Torgallmenningen used similar descriptors for Festplassen).</p> <p>Half of the respondents described the social aspect as that which they enjoyed best at Torgallmenningen.</p> <p>When asked what they would improve, many answered with ideas that would improve/increase the social aspects even more: more benches, enclosed playground for children, permanent electrical wiring for traveling musicians.</p>

The Social and Emotional descriptors revealed a pattern that follow the hypothesis. Very many people wished to change Festplassen to be more cozy and intimate, more green and nice and filled with more benches. People seemed to express the desire to use Festplassen in a more sociable manner, and implied that they would if the space were changed to accommodate social activity. These responses follow the pattern revealed by the Emotional descriptors.

In an attempt to remove the confounding factor of physical location, we asked the subjects a control question about the opposite plaza. When people stood at Torgallmenningen, they expressed more negativity to Festplassen and thought that it was a boring, uninteresting place. However, when they stood at Festplassen, the aesthetic and sculptural aspects came forth more clearly. It appears that the immediate physical experience of Festplassen gives stronger aesthetic associations than when people think of it as a remote location.

In addition, one researcher asked the respondents “*Which of the two urban spaces do you prefer?*”. The great majority of people felt that Torgallmenningen was their favorite.

Control Questions

Two questions were included to extract more specific meaningful descriptors than neutral ones which were non-offensive to the researchers. This strategy also gave the subject more time to think and greater capacity to reveal their true opinion better than vague and ambiguous adjectives. The first question was: “*What do you like best about Festplassen/Torgallmenningen?*”.

Fig. 5: Comparison of what respondents like best about either Torgallmenningen or Festplassen

At Festplassen, it was apparent that the physical attributes were in the forefront of people’s experience. For the majority of respondents, the periodic activities held at Festplassen were an integral part of the respondents’ experience. None of the subjects responded with Symbolic, Emotional, or Social aspects as a primary characteristic. Interestingly, the results were almost opposite for Torgallmenningen. Almost half of the respondents liked the Social aspects of Torgallmenningen best. These results reveal the most fundamental distinction between the two plazas. Peter Butenschön and Maren Hersleth Holsen conclude that a *place* is something different than a *public area*. A place gathers meaning due to its activities and cultural history, and provides a reference for both peoples’ individual experience and their association to the city as a whole (Butenschön and Hersleth, 2003).

The second question was: “*What would you like to change about Festplassen/Torgallmenningen?*”. The responses for this question built upon and emphasized the established understanding. At Festplassen, most people described Situational/Material

characteristics such as benches, more trees to make it cozy, flowers, and permanent art installations. Many respondents also expressed a wish for increased frequency of social and cultural activities such as dance exhibitions and concerts. In general, people wanted to change Festplassen into a more social public space. In general, people at Torgallmenningen wanted the place to either remain as it is today, or to intensify the current identifying characteristics of the plaza. In contradiction to this, the respondents at Festplassen expressed a desire to radically alter the fundamental identity of the space.

Fig. 6: Comparison of what respondents would like to change

The Danish architect Jan Gehl (2003) demonstrates that it is not the formal architectural of a space that determines its value, but rather its degree of integration into the existing urban structure and social life. The manner in which the space communicates with people is determined by the simplicity or the complexity. These aspects appear to be of vital importance to the pedestrians at Festplassen. Festplassen does not communicate its identifying qualities to the people as Torgallmenningen does. People seem to want to establish an emotional connection to places, including Festplassen.

4.2 Epilogue

The object for this study was to compare two spaces in order to find out more about one. Perhaps the best way to compare them is to listen to the residents who encounter both places on a regular basis:

Quotes about Torgallmenningen:

- “It’s generally a nice place to be” Female student from Sogndal

- “The columns ruin it, both aesthetically and politically.” Male shopkeeper
- “The sound is much too loud, especially when something is going on. The sound can be heard from Fløyen!” Male retiree (NB: Fløyen is the mountain closest to Bergen with a highly-popular observation deck that overlooks the city. The deck is quite far away)

Quotes about Festplassen:

- “It makes you want to dance tango” Female civil architect
- “A little too much asphalt” Female county administrator
(NB: there is no asphalt on the site, only granite)
- “So nice but so slippery”. Female retiree
- “Very, very, VERY ugly” Male shopkeeper
- “Its well-designed in relation to its surroundings”. Male retiree

5. Conclusion

This paper investigates how/if a powerful design parameter (white space) can be translated from 2-dimensions into 3-dimensional experience of public space. It is important to keep in mind that white space is an active part of a composition, even though it is the space around, in between objects. When applied successfully, it is not simply negative space, which implies that it is an empty void and lacks purpose. Rather, it becomes a necessary, complementary aspect to positive elements. When used sensitively and conscientiously, white space is a powerful design parameter. When applied less successfully, it can appear empty, lacking in purpose and an afterthought.

In our study into white space in an urban arena, we found that (per our hypothesis) white space is considered *empty* at Festplassen, a space that represents graphic white space in three dimensions. Based on subject responses, we can conclude that white space does not create a socially attractive area. Rather, it creates a space where formal and informal recreational/entertainment activities can be held. From the respondent’s descriptions, we can assume that if an urban space is intended to be a social meeting point, people want to see it filled with things: not only people but physical attributes and colors!

It is our opinion that white space must be given a proactive role in all aspects of design, in both 2- and 3-dimensional design. To do this, it is necessary to understand the relationship of white space to the associations it creates in people who see and/or interact with it.

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